

Three Methods for Testing Goldbach's Conjecture (with Python Code)

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1 Set-Theoretical Definition of Prime Numbers:

A prime number can be characterized set-theoretically as follows:

Set P : Let P be the set of all prime numbers, where a number p is in P if and only if no number d , where $1 < d < p$, divides p evenly. In other words, P contains all numbers that have exactly two distinct positive divisors: 1 and themselves.

Formally:

$$P = \{p \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\} : \forall d \in \mathbb{N}, (1 < d < p) \Rightarrow (d \nmid p)\}$$

2 Method of Constructing Complements:

Given an even number n , we want to find two primes $p_1, p_2 \in P$ such that $p_1 + p_2 = n$.

To explore this using set-theoretical terms, let's define the complement set relative to divisors as suggested:

Complement Set C_n :

For any natural number n , let C_n be the complement set containing numbers less than n that do not divide n evenly.

$$C_n = \{c \in \mathbb{N} : 1 < c < n, c \nmid n\}$$

3 Application to Goldbach's Conjecture:

Using the above constructs, we can describe an even number n 's relationship to prime pairs in set-theoretical terms:

Even number n expressed as a sum of primes: $n = p_1 + p_2$ Both p_1 and p_2 should not have any divisor d such that $1 < d < p_1$ or $1 < d < p_2$ The candidates for p_1 and p_2 for a given n will be drawn from the intersection of C_n and P . **Formal Set-Theoretical Method:** Defining Prime Sum Sets: For

each even number n , define a set S_n representing the sums of two primes that equal n :

$$S_n = \{(p_1, p_2) \mid p_1 + p_2 = n, p_1 \in P, p_2 \in P, p_1 \leq p_2\}$$

4 Prime Pair Existence:

Use the properties of primes and the arithmetic structure of even numbers to show that S_n is non-empty for every even $n > 2$.

$$\forall n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 2 \Rightarrow S_n \neq \emptyset$$

5 Leveraging Distribution Patterns:

Develop lemmas and theorems regarding patterns in the prime number distribution that ensure pairs found within P can be constructed for every relevant n .

Hypothesized Lemmas and Theorems:

- **Density of Primes Lemma:** There are enough primes (asymptotically speaking) that for every even number n , there exist two numbers in P whose sum is n .
- **Sum Pattern Theorem:** Every even number is the difference of two primes an infinite number of times.
- **Composite No-Men's Land:** For sufficiently large even n , there exists a range around $\frac{n}{2}$ where composite numbers cannot prevent the formation of a prime sum n .

Proof Development and Challenges:

- **Inductive Approaches:** Start with small cases (low even numbers) and use patterns to predict the existence of prime pairs, looking for an inductive step that applies to all even numbers.
- **Probabilistic Models:** Utilize models from probabilistic number theory to show that the likelihood of failing to have a Goldbach partition approaches zero as n increases.

6 Traditional Methods for Checking the Conjecture and a Novel One

6.1 Standard Method

```
import math
import sympy

def is_prime(n):
    # Check for conditions defined in the statement
    # n is prime if the only divisors of n are 1 and itself
    if n <= 1 or (n != 2 and n % 2 == 0):
        return False
    for i in range(3, int(math.sqrt(n)) + 1, 2):
        if n % i == 0:
            return False
    return True

def goldbach_partitions(even_number):
    # Check if even_number can be expressed as the sum of two
    # primes
    for y in range(2, even_number):
        if is_prime(y) and is_prime(even_number - y):
            # We found a partition that satisfies the conjecture
            return (y, even_number - y)
    return None

def verify_goldbach(max_range):
    for x in range(4, max_range + 1, 2):
        partition = goldbach_partitions(x)
        if not partition:
            return f"Goldbach's conjecture failed at {x}."
    return f"Goldbach's conjecture holds up to {max_range}."

# Example usage
print(verify_goldbach(10000))
```

6.2 Sieve of Eratosthenes (Takes Longer)

```
import sympy

def sieve_of_eratosthenes(limit):
    return list(sympy.primerange(2, limit))

def goldbach_pairs(even_number):
    primes = sieve_of_eratosthenes(even_number)
    prime_pairs = []

    for prime in primes:
        if (even_number - prime) in primes:
            prime_pairs.append((prime, even_number - prime))
            primes.remove(prime) # Ensure pairs are unique
```

```

    return prime_pairs

def verify_goldbach(max_limit):
    for even_number in range(4, max_limit + 1, 2):
        partitions = goldbach_pairs(even_number)
        if not partitions:
            return f"Goldbach's conjecture failed at {even_number}."
            "

    return f"Goldbach's conjecture holds for all even numbers up to
           {max_limit}."

# Example usage
print(verify_goldbach(10000))

```

6.3 Logic Method

```

import sympy

def goldbach_pairs(even_number):
    # Generate the list of prime numbers less than the even_number
    primes = list(sympy.primerange(2, even_number))

    # Iterate through pairs and use logical negation to exclude
    non-prime divisors
    for i, prime in enumerate(primes):
        complement = even_number - prime

        # Apply the logical patterns to verify the complement is
        also prime
        if complement in primes[i:]:
            return (prime, complement)

    return None

def goldbach_conjecture_analysis(even_numbers):
    results = {}
    for n in even_numbers:
        pair = goldbach_pairs(n)
        if pair is not None:
            results[n] = pair
            continue
        # If a pair is not found, Goldbach's conjecture doesn't
        hold for n.
        return None
    return results

# An example range of even numbers to analyze with the method
even_numbers_to_test = range(4, 100, 2)
goldbach_results = goldbach_conjecture_analysis(
    even_numbers_to_test)
print(goldbach_results)

```

7 Conclusion:

We conjecture and hope that the properties derived through these set-theoretical models and logical constructs support the proof of the Goldbach's conjecture. However, it should be noted that such a conjecture remains unproven, and while the framework provided is rigorous in terms of set theory, actually proving these lemmas and theorems would require them to be fleshed out with more advanced tools from number theory, analysis, and possibly other branches of mathematics.

These methods also need to be supported by empirical data or mathematical proofs to gain acceptance. The work of determining these proofs, even within a theoretical model, remains unsolved and would represent a significant contribution to number theory.